

Flow dynamics during the hydrocarbon exploitation for prevention and management of water venues in oil field: A study case of Crystal field in Chad

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1 Abstract

Water management in any oil field is a challenge. This is particularly true when producer wells are drilled on a mature field, that has produced for some time and had already experienced a water breakthrough.

The Crystal field is in the Doba basin at 430 km south of N'Djamena (Figure 1). The field was discovered with CRY-01 well drilled by ExxonMobil in 2002 which proved the presence of hydrocarbons in Upper and Lower Cretaceous. From 2012, intensive drilling campaigns were conducted to develop the oil potential of the field. Two wells were drilled in 2012 and 28 wells were drilled from 2013 to 2019 including horizontal oil producers and water injector / disposal wells.

The production started in 2013 and reached a peak of 15 000 bopd in December 2014 from 3 reservoirs (Figure 2):

- The reservoir A (Upper cretaceous) produced by 12 wells including 10 horizontal wells. To date, the reservoir A cumulated 10.5 MMstb of oil leading to a recovery factor (RF) of 5% (OIP estimated at 192 MMstb).
- The reservoir C (Lower Cretaceous) is produced by 6 wells and cumulated 6.7 MMstb of oil leading to a RF of 17% (OIP estimated at 40 MMstb).

- The reservoir D (Lower Cretaceous) is produced by 6 wells and cumulated 8.6 MMstb of oil leading to a RF of 18% (OIP estimated at 47 MMstb).

2. Introduction

Horizontal drilling has many advantages; however, the main elements of water site control are hydrostatic pressure management through forage fluids (suitable mud), the use of detection tools (probes), clogging techniques, tracers, and annular volume monitoring to control, detect, and manage water inflows.

The essential parameters for controlling water inflow are:

Drilling Fluid Management (Mud):

- ✓ Use of drilling muds adapted to the geology, which is essential for consolidating the wellbore and controlling pressure.
- ✓ Mud density to maintain pressure higher than that of the formation to prevent inflow (hydrostatic pressure);
- ✓ Real-time monitoring via a probe located at the wellhead to control the direction and identify areas of high-water pressure;
- ✓ Detection of tracers in the drilling mud to check for groundwater contamination;
- ✓ Use of sealing techniques in the event of loss of circulation or water inflow; for this purpose, sealing products are injected to plug fissures in the formation;
- ✓ Pressure monitoring in horizontal wells: The well must be closed as soon as any water flow is detected, as monitoring is carried out by measuring the pressure at the wellhead and using heavy plugs;
- ✓ Safety and Prevention: A preliminary geological study is necessary to identify aquifers, i.e., areas with high water levels.

Figure 1: An overview of the Crystal field in Badila a) All the reservoirs, b) Reservoir A

Tableau 1 :

Reservoir unit	OWC (mTDSS)	STOIIP (MMstb)
A2.1	-615	77
A2.2	-615	74

The field is divided into several independent dynamic units, the main ones being reservoirs A2.1 and A2.2. All the producer wells are horizontal, targeting only one reservoir unit [2] [3].

In order to fully develop the field and increase its recovery factor, drilling more horizontal producer wells on the flank of the reservoirs, closer to the Water Oil contact would be logical. However, those wells could be closer to water ingress and could experience quick water breakthrough and small reserves [4] [5].

A reservoir model has been built using CMG Imex software with 50mx50m grid size for a total of around 509,000 cells. The main objective of this model was to evaluate how much those downdip wells could recover. The figure below shows the result of this simulation for the reservoir A.2.1 [6].

Figure 4 : Result of simulation model for the reservoir A.2.1.

Figure 5 : 4 Field Cumulation oil in Reservoir A.2.1.

The same reservoir simulation model was also used to evaluate the interest of the downdip wells for the reservoir A.2.2 [7] [8] [9].

Figure 6 : Result of simulation model for the reservoir A.2.2.

Figure 7 : Field Cumulation oil in Reservoir A.2.2.

In both cases, the reservoir model forecast lower reserves for the flank wells because of early water breakthrough [10]. In order to increase the well reserves and delay the water, a specific lower completion using AICD and open hole swell packer was installed in the drain section [11] [12].

4. Horizontal drains drilling strategy

The wells were drilled in 12-1/4in hole size to the top of the reservoir target. A 9-5/8in Casing was then run and the drain itself were drilled in 8-1/2in hole size [13]. Landing and navigation within the reservoir are a very important phase of the project. Both reservoir layers A2.2 and A2.1 are not very thick (Between 10m and 25m) [14] [15].

Landing at the top of the reservoir was achieved using LWD-GR tools with an offset to the drill bit of about 15m. It was then very important to have good correlation with the layers above, and also use mud logging data. The angle of well was designed to be 5deg more than the dip angle of the formation [15].

The placement of the drain section within the reservoir was done geometrically, again keeping an inclination slightly higher than the predicted dip of the formation. Contingency plans were ready in case the well exited the sand too early, but in practice, this situation never occurred [16][17].

This strategy was very different than the one followed by the previous operator who relied on geosteering with a more complete LWD logging suite [18]. The well was landed horizontally within the targeted sand, and then the trajectory was adjusted when LWD tools were showing a proximity to the shale layers [19].

Figure 8 : Horizontal drain drilling oil well

5. Production results

All wells performed very well in terms of production, exceeding the results of the reservoir model, in terms of Productivity Index, Water cut development, and production decline. The P8 well was particularly interesting because it was a downdip well with risk of early water breakthrough. It has been producing for 6 months, with absolutely no water [20]. The other wells had all better productivity than forecasted. It is believed with the navigation strategy put in place; the drains crossed the reservoir layer in its best position. The previous navigation strategy was positioning the drains at the very top of the reservoir very close to the shale layer [21].

The graphs below show the current and extrapolated production versus of the 8 new wells, compared with the forecast from the reservoir simulation. As can be seen on both graphs, there is a very good accordance between current production and forecast from the model.

Figure 9: New wells production versus forecast

Figure 10: New wells cumulative oil production versus forecast

6. Development strategy

After this drilling campaign, the Recovery Factor of the A reservoir is expected to jump to 23%, which is a very good result. However, that good production could unlock a second drilling campaign, as they have shown that downdip drains, closer to the OWC, have interesting reserves.

Therefore, it is probably possible to reach 30 or even 40% Recovery Factor when the Crystal field is fully developed. This is far higher than surrounding fields in Chad and could unlock a wave of redevelopment on those fields.

7. Results of oil recovery in Crystal field

Tableau 2 :

	STOIIP (MMstb)	Np_08/2025 (MMstb)	Actuel RF (%)	RF Do Nothing (Aout 2037-%)	RF after Crystal PHASE 1 campaign (Aout 2037-%)
Reservoir A	152	14.3	9,4%	15.7%	23%
Reservoir C	40	7.7	19.3%	25.0%	25.0%
Reservoir D	47	9.5	20.2%	27.2%	27.2%

There is an interesting technique to evaluate how efficient a plan of development has been with respect to water management. It consists in plotting the Recovery factor on the Y axis, and the Water Oil Ratio on the x axis.

Figure 11 : Analog field reservoir WOR evolution vs Recovery Factor (RF)

Those graphs have been plotted for the Crystal field “A reservoir” and a similar field located in the same basin, having roughly the same oil viscosity. This analog field has been developed with vertical wells only, producing in a commingled way several layers. Water management was thus not integrated in the development strategy. This field as a recovery factor

of 25% and a WOR of 30 now, which represent a BSW of 97%. In other words, this particular field is now very close to the economic limit.

Figure 12: Crystal field A reservoir WOR evolution vs Recovery factor (RF)

On the other hand, the Crystal field has a recovery factor of 7% already, but is producing almost no water (WOR less than 1.5%) which is showing how efficient the development strategy based on horizontal wells with AICD is.

Figure 12 : Typical well completion

Figure 13 : Area of the study zone

8. Conclusions

The development strategy based on horizontal wells targeting one single sand has worked quite well. Recovery factors of up to 40% are theoretically possible, which is much higher than nearby fields developed by other operators using solely vertical wells commingling all reservoirs. This old strategy has led to excessive water production that cannot be managed, and the fields developed this way have a low Recovery Factor.

This document examines the challenges associated with managing water influx in hydrocarbon exploitation in mature oil fields, based on a case study of the Crystal field in Chad. The analysis focuses on practical aspects such as reservoir behavior, horizontal well positioning, and water control strategies.

The objective is to integrate geological elements, reservoir modeling, and production performance, while emphasizing the importance of optimizing hydrocarbon recovery rates while delaying water breakthroughs to improve the profitability of operations. The results highlight the value of modeling and development optimization in mature fields, while detailing Cretaceous reservoirs (Upper and Lower A, C, and D) with STOIP estimates and key recovery factors.

In conclusion, these operational results highlight the potential of integrated modeling, optimized well positioning, and custom completion designs in the development of mature fields.

9. Recommendations

This strategy should be followed for the other fields in Chad in the Doba bassin. The recent drilling campaign has furthermore shown some areas of improvement:

- Regular acid job, both HCl and HF can mitigate scale formation and fines migration in the lower completion: This helps keep the Productivity Index high and, in the end, helps boost the field production.
- Changes to the lower completion design could be made for future wells: up to now, oil swellable packers have been used with a rather low expansion ratio (They can expand up to 9in, whereas the drain OD is 8-1/2in). There are therefore some doubts about their efficiency in the long run.
- For future wells, the number of well packers could be increased and water swellable packers could be added, with a higher expansion ratio, in order to ensure full isolation between each drain section
- Water injection wells should be drilled to provide better pressure support, but given the contrast between zones, careful choice of perforated interval and potential selectivity should be part of their design

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